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Research Article

**SPECTRUM OF HISTOPATHOLGY SPECIMEN RECEIVED
AFTER OPEN OR LAPROSCOPIC CHOLECYSTECTOMY IN
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Abstract:

Background: Cholecystectomy is the most procedure performed in hospital these days. often this is followed by histopathology examination. The objective of this study is to find out the spectrum of diseases as this varies from country to country.

Materials and Methods: It was a cross sectional study in the department of Pathology for the period of six months. Data of only those gallbladder specimens was included in the study who had a confirmed diagnosis of gallstones using ultrasonography. Data was computed on Statistical Package for Social Sciences. Data was analyzed using software and interpreted in the form of frequencies and percentages.

Results: A total of six hundred and forty-four samples were included. Various age groups were seen but most specimens received they belonged to patients of 41-60 years age group. There was predominance of specimens from female subjects. Most common pathological diagnosis was chronic cholecystitis.

Conclusion: Chronic cholecystitis is the most common finding encountered. The frequency of carcinoma gallbladder carcinoma was very low.

Keywords: spectrum, gallbladder, female

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INTRODUCTION:

Prevalence of gall stones is on the spike due to sedentary life style and obesity epidemic [1]. The incidence varies among different parts of the world. It is lowest in Black African (less than 5%) and highest in American Indian (64-73%) [2]. In India incidence is around 10-22% while 11% in Pakistan [2,3]. Gallstones can present with many forms and rarely with complications [4]. Risk factors are many and symptoms may appear suddenly [2, 5]. Treatment option include surgery or newer modalities which are less commonly used [6, 7]. After resection of gallbladder, it is sent for histopathological examination. Moreover, the prognosis of advanced carcinoma gallbladder is very poor which is mentioned in this research paper. [8]

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

A cross sectional was conducted in 2016 in the department of Histopathology, Fauji Foundation Hospital, Rawalpindi. All samples received from operating theaters were included in the research after proper handling. Proper histopathology protocols were followed. The data was collected by the investigators with the help of Self-Administered Proforma sheet. Data was put in Statistical Package for Social Sciences Version 21. Data analysis was done.

RESULTS:

The study sample consisted of 644 patients. The age of the patients was divided into 5 groups. 389 (60.4 %) patients were between the ages of 41-60 years, 126 (19.6%) patients were between the ages of 61-80 years whereas 107 (16.6%) were between 21-40 years and 14 (2.2%) were less than 20 years old. The study showed female preponderance.

When noted, it was found out that the majority of the participants had dyspepsia, pain in hypochondrium and pain along with vomiting for visiting hospitals. Different patterns of histopathological lesions were found in the reports, chronic cholecystitis being the most common accounting for almost 80% cases. When examined carefully, gallstones were present in majority of the patients.

DISCUSSION:

Our study cohort comprised of a large and mixed sample. There was female predominance in study sample for all age groups. Most samples were from women of 40 plus years age group. Females were more commonly affected. It is believed that many factors contribute to this factor as mentioned in this paper [2] most common finding was chronic

cholecystitis followed by acute cholecystitis. This contributes to major elective cases performed in any surgical hospital. The prevalence of gallstones are increased because of female sex, multiple children and obesity. Health care system needs to adopt new policy to counter those issues. More researches should be performed to clear the views.

CONCLUSION:

Chronic cholecystitis is the most common finding encountered. The frequency of gallbladder carcinoma was very low. The study showed female dominance.

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